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EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF CRITICAL THINKING

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History of critical thinking

Etymology can, in many cases, help to understand what the words themselves should mean. When trying to understand critical thinking, as a current present in the academic environment, looking at this meaning is extremely important.

According to the online Portuguese dictionary Dicio 2022, “thought is the act of thinking, becoming aware, reflecting or meditating. Faculty of conceiving, combining and comparing ideas; intelligence”. On the other hand, if the critic, also defined by Dicio, is: “relative to criticism, which is based on criteria, which establishes a value judgment for artistic, scientific, etc.”

In this way, it can be understood that critical thinking, unlike what can be assumed at another time, that it could be linked to the depreciation of something or someone, is related to the reflection on the value and contribution that a positioning, vision or idea can bring. Critical thinking is actually a tool to encourage learning and change the state of knowledge. See what he says in his article Training in Critical Thinking for Science Teachers: impact on classroom practices and students’ level of critical

thinking, CELINA TENREIRO-VIEIRA, 2004:

The results obtained support the conclusion that: teachers’ training in critical thinking influences teaching practices in relation to the teaching of critical thinking; and different critical thinking training programs influence teaching practices in critical thinking differently. Teachers who received training in critical thinking changed their practices regarding critical thinking, which became significantly “more” conducive to critical thinking.

In this way, with the globalization of information occurring instantly all over the world, it becomes increasingly necessary to analyze and investigate everything that has access, not only to investigate the veracity, but also to exercise the correct deepening of knowledge.

The Eleva platform, in an article published on its website on September 8, 2020, defines Critical Thinking as follows: “Critical thinking is the ability to analyze topics with clarity and

rationality, understanding information in an objective way and with ample capacity for judgment . Applied in the school environment and in life as a whole, it is something that involves the analysis of resources, phenomena, facts, dates and other references to assist in strategic decision making.”

When considering the importance of Critical Thinking in the school environment, several countries have already adapted their curriculum and effectively started the approach with their faculty, which in the medium term tends to raise the level of knowledge of teachers and students around the world.

Also according to Plataforma Eleva (2020) “Critical thinking is a habit. It is something that must be developed continuously, with the help of educators and family members. It is interconnected with analytical capacity, which also highlights the need for emotions are put on the back burner.” Considering then that the learning process accelerates when the student is encouraged to step out of their comfort zone and separate personal opinions from facts, through research and fundamentals.

Preparing faculty for teaching the practice of critical thinking actually brings significant changes to the promotion of critical thinking. Such practices, to which these teachers were submitted, including aspects of knowledge acquisition, appropriate methodology for the construction of curricular materials, or even, playful activities that promote critical thinking, promoting training in critical thinking on the part of these teachers, were significantly higher in in relation to teachers who were trained with a focus only on developing their critical thinking skills, according to Celina, 2004.

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It is possible to observe in society, a portion that is not concerned with the veracity of the information they receive, the news they read, the scientific studies that guide academic life and especially the formation of elementary and high school. It is a youth disconnected from basic and fundamental values in life in society.

The questioning in search of knowledge, very present in philosophy, is somehow abandoned by this post-modern generation, which needs to receive information on a “kissed hand”. In his article Why you don’t like philosophy and maybe it’s not your fault; the author, Felipe Diego, 2018 says :

The best way to explain the path that leads someone to become an idealist or a pragmatist can be summarized in three points: (1) the lack of motivation when studying Philosophy or the absence of the correct motivation. (2) the complexity of the content itself and its time of presentation, or (3) the eventual ‘scare-off’ of the subject. It is essential to understand that, in any well-developed theory, each point implies the other [5] , so perhaps the redundancy of parts

of this text is a sign that I am speaking the truth.

Felipe lists three main points of the lack of interest in philosophy, in philosophizing, in the search for knowledge in a way that knowledge is loved, as well as describing the etymology of the word philosophy. Of these, the first may be the most intriguing, because motivation, which is what motivates us to act, which makes us leave our comfort zone, of inertia, is also the most subjective of them, as each individual can bring itself, different motivations for each action it performs.

This also highlights the importance of motivating students to this search for philosophical thinking. Encouraging this search for knowledge, questioning in a correct, scientific way, questioning not only to leave the interlocutor in a moment of embarrassment, but questioning in order to reach the point where the importance of that theme, subject, information and research is perceived.

The questioning here, whether understood as critical or philosophical thinking, does not come only as a refutation of ideas and thoughts, but also as a way of ratifying what is discussed, as well as its importance in contributing to academic development.

It is necessary to create an environment conducive to the evolution of this thought, the student cannot be expected to develop this skill overnight, it is necessary to take root during the stages and phases of their teaching. See what Felipe says about it:

Now the second point. Think about the process of building a house: first the foundations are built, then the walls and finally the roof. If construction started with the roof, you wouldn't build

a house, but an aberration that someone would call modern art. Like a house, human knowledge has a hierarchical structure of construction. First, start with simple things and then get to complex things. When we talk about knowledge, the path is from perception (concrete) to concepts (abstract). The further away from your perception, the more complex it is to grasp the concept [10].

In this way, it is necessary to create a basis for the construction of this philosophical thought and, consequently, of critical thinking. A student cannot be expected to arrive at university knowing how to perform complex mathematical calculations, without having had a basis for doing so during his high school education. In this way, we will now see how critical thinking is developed in the school environment.

Development of Critical Thinking in the School Environment

The school is a new place of socialization for the student and the classroom is a place of dialogue where the teacher and the student exchange knowledge, allowing everyone to have their points of view exposed, so that they can debate and understand subjects, for that, it is necessary to develop critical thinking.

The formation of critical thinking begins to happen mostly within the educational environment, where the student is faced with certain situations where he needs to have an initial observation and develop from this observation a critical judgment.

Critical thinking is a complex skill, it is not innate but developed throughout

life, within the educational environment this skill has to be stimulated, so that the student leaves school and enters universities already aware of the need for the think has, to continue improving critical thinking.

Unlike what is thought, the development of critical thinking begins in childhood, at the beginning of the child's school life, work and activities may already be being developed that stimulate thinking and thus developing the student's creativity and perception of the world.

When the student arrives in high school the LDB in its art. 35, clarifies that secondary education has as one of its purposes to promote "the improvement of the student as a human person, including ethical training and the development of intellectual autonomy and critical thinking". In order to promote critical thinking in high school, teachers can take advantage of classroom debates, as well as the many technologies that we have today, in addition to sensory, creative and theatrical activities.

It is necessary for educators to think about the materials to be worked on, in order to promote greater student interest, so that they begin to look at everything around them more critically, since critical thinking cannot be conditioned to walls. According to Rainbolt, "the commitment to critical thinking entails basing our beliefs on good arguments, which makes us happier, as opposed to basing them on bad arguments, which leaves us in the hands of chance".

Currently, the load of information dispensed on individuals within society and that need to be processed and understood by them, so that they can take a position in front of this sea of

information, and thus be able to look at the world critically enough to have a positioning and absorb the best.

It is necessary to understand the importance of works aimed at the formation of critical thinking, Tenreiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000), are emphatic in defending the concern of promoting critical thinking, for these:

The explanation of the growing importance and need for teaching critical thinking lies above all in the fact that critical thinking is a cornerstone in the formation of individuals capable of facing and dealing with the continuous change of the increasingly complex systems that characterize the current world (TENREIRO-VIEIRA and VIEIRA, 2000, p. 14) Therefore, the development of critical thinking in societies is notorious and emerging, as stated by Tenreiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000).

Therefore, it is understood the responsibility that the school has to form autonomous and critical citizens for the world they are inserted in, where there is a growing demand for students who have a careful look at everyday situations, where discernment will allow you to form your own opinions based on well-founded concepts.

Critical Thinking and Student-Researcher Training

In summary, we can summarize that Critical Thinking is a cognitive skill that involves analysis, logical reasoning and clinical judgment, oriented to problem solving and outstanding in training and practice. When applied to research, it opens up the possibility of enhancing other rationalities for the engagement of the various knowledge systems,

the training and professionalization of teachers, professionals in general and the university community, strengthening content and knowledge based on sustainable values and practices, with a view to making an accurate decision and achieving effective results. (MAGALHÃES, TERNEIRO-VIEIRA, 2006)

The ongoing social transformations increasingly demand research and training concepts and strategies for scientific and technological development.

The knowledge focuses are consolidated, having as references the studies about the effects of the problem on the dialogues, often interdisciplinary, allowing a new horizon for the diagnosis of social changes, breaking with reductionism and opening space for a reality permeated by uncertainties, which allows the formulation of different approaches. (JACOBI, 2012).

However, interdisciplinarity implies a knowledge process that seeks to establish transversal cuts in the understanding and explanation of the research context, aiming at the interaction between disciplines, overcoming the scientific compartmentalization caused by excessive specialization. As a combination of several areas of knowledge, interdisciplinarity presupposes the development of interactive methodologies, configuring the scope of focus. (SCHMIDT, GOMES, JACOBI, 2019). The ongoing social transformations increasingly demand interdisciplinary concepts to guide research and policy-making and development strategies, and the effects of current economic policies on the dynamics and living conditions of societies must be recognized (FUNTOWICZ, 2000).

According to Wals, 2007, the emphasis on practices that encourage interdisciplinarity and transversality reveals the great potential that exists to leave the common place and work with themes that incite changes in behavior, social responsibility and ethics, which stimulates another look, demonstrating the importance of understanding the complexity involved in the processes and the challenge of having a more reflective and active attitude, forming more responsible, careful and engaged professionals in collaborative processes with the context of society.

In this way, what is sought as the most effective teaching methodology in science education is a proposal that aims to obtain learning, scientific concepts and topics with meaning, where argumentation and the development of critical thinking are the main objective. (GUIMARÃES, MASSONI, 2020)

The concept of argumentation, based on the triad affirmative, justification and evidence, is centered on the idea of understanding science as an argument and of teaching it under the bias of argumentation. (KUHN, 1991, 1993, 2014).

For Kuhn, in this tripartite conception, the statement contained in an argument is a theory, a point of view, an idea or an opinion that one wants to prove; justification is the reason or cause that supports the claim and connects it with the evidence, observation, fact or data that supports or supports the claim.

Research promotes ways of thinking and reasoning in a meaningful way and that is closer to the way scientists do/build science, that is, always looking to review their reasoning and highlighting the mutable, provisional and not definitive aspect both in the process of developing the scientific knowledge as

well as its teaching.

CONCLUSION

According to the authors analyzed and the results obtained, critical thinking can be understood as a term related to criticism, which is based on some criterion, which establishes a value judgment for artistic, scientific works, for example.

Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or actively evaluating information collected or generated by observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication. In this way, critical thinking can be understood as an instrument that is capable of boosting learning and changing knowledge in a strategic way.

Countries around the world have been promoting critical thinking through the provision of training content, continuing education for teachers on issues related to Critical Thinking.

In this context, raising the level of knowledge of teachers and, consequently, of students, as observed by Celina Terneiro-Vieira (2004), who, through her results, supports that training in critical thinking for faculty is essential for promoting and passing on knowledge about this knowledge to students through teaching practices.

It is worth mentioning that the training in Critical Thinking of teachers with a focus only on their particular capacities for the development of Critical Thinking was not effective for this transfer of knowledge to the student body to happen, because a training based on appropriate methodologies for this transfer to happen is necessary. , that is, the teacher needs to learn to pass on

this type of knowledge through specific tools and methods, not only to know what critical knowledge and theories about this theme are about.

In this way, the student body becomes able to discern and analyze in an investigative and efficient way the veracity of the information accessed in this globalized world. Furthermore, the authors agree that developing critical thinking is a particular task and should be seen as “habit building” and that it should also be based on facts rather than personal opinions and emotions.

Celina terneiro-Vieira (2004) and Felipe Diego (2018) agree that the search for knowledge must be based on facts, in a scientific way, as stimulating critical and logical thinking in students can bring positive and significant changes. In this context, each student brings with him different motivations that may or may not direct him to the search for knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary that the student body loves knowledge, as well as the search for it. In experimental practice classes, in integral education schools, for example, the search for knowledge is stimulated in order to develop the logical thinking of students, in a way that knowledge is rooted through the stages of teaching with employment. a solid theoretical basis and well-designed and executed practices.

Terneiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000), Celina terneiro-Vieira (2004) and Felipe Diego (2018) share the idea that it is necessary to train autonomous and critical students, responsible for the construction of their own knowledge, as there is a need to train students with a refined and critical look so that they can deal with the changes of the modern world.

Magalhães, Terneiro-Vieira (2006) shows that critical thinking applied to

research leads to the professionalization of teachers and the training of professionals in general, strengthening content and knowledge based on sustainable values and practices, with a view to accurate decision making and reaching effective results.

It is necessary to highlight that scientific compartmentalization, for example, in laboratory practices of natural sciences and mathematics, leads to a blockage in the construction of knowledge. On the other hand, interdisciplinarity implies a knowledge process that seeks to establish transversal cuts in the understanding and explanation of the research context. In other words, when interdisciplinarity is worked on, a greater scope of focus can be accessed. In this context, it is important to highlight the continuous search of civilizations for social development that can only be achieved through technological development and quality education (SCHMIDT, GOMES, JACOBI, 2019).

Therefore, the importance of education and its effects on current public and economic policies must be recognized, as this education is responsible for the formation of more responsible, careful professionals engaged in collaborative processes with the context of society, which leads us to technological and social development so desired (FUNTOWICZ, 2000).

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